

Harmonization of Advanced Materials Ecosystems serving strategic Innovation Markets to pave the way to a Digital Materials & Product Passport

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Coordination and knowledge sharing across materials development communities (CSA)

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1. Preamble

The overarching objective of DigiPass-CSA (call topic HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-39, Grant Agreement No 101138510) is to enhance the digital maturity of the European communities that develop materials and intermediate products. The project develops recommendations and clear routes toward digitalized circular business models. The overarching key result of DigiPass is to create a sustainable platform which includes support for Digital Materials & Product Passport and for collaborative innovation-by-design processes in a circular economy served by Advanced Materials (AM). A business model for operating such a platform completes the overarching objective.

DigiPass takes the position that accelerating the design, development, and production of advanced, safe, and sustainable chemicals and materials calls for a collaborative approach involving different stakeholders within value networks to support durability, R-strategies and recyclability of products. The DigiPass consortium consists of Universities, RTOs, companies and Industrial Associations dominated by SMEs, and thus represents a relevant cross-sectorial stakeholder structure as targeted by the Advanced Materials Act (AMA).

2. DigiPass Integration of Innovation and Production: Lessons learned

Companies in the export-oriented European industry are integrated into European and worldwide, complex supply networks. The shortage of raw materials in Europe makes it necessary to ensure industrial value creation through constant innovations in materials, manufacturing and production, based on (imports of) raw and recycled materials and intermediate products, to maintain and regain industrial leadership in an internationally drastically changing context.

On the European side, strategic goals have been proclaimed that are based on the European *Green Deal* and have already been taken up legislatively at the European level. Above all, the *Data Act*, the *AI Act*, the *TEN-E Regulation*, the *Critical Raw Materials Act*, and the *Net Zero Industry Act* should be mentioned here as key initiatives supporting the accelerated roll-out of clean energy and manufacturing according to the European *Clean Industrial Deal*. Elements of which can already be found for example in the *Ecodesign for Sustainable Product Regulation* (ESPR), in particular the plans to introduce Digital Product Passports as measures to support the transition to a circular European economy are to be implemented by the industry soon. The European *Twin Green&Digital Transition process* is therefore not an option, but rather the future basis of economic activity.

Accelerating advanced materials design, development and upscaling should be recognized as a key regulatory priority under the Advanced Materials Act (AMA). In this context, the development of cost-effective, cloud-based, and interoperable digital solutions, such as digital product passport platforms, digital twins, predictive lifetime modelling tools (both AI- and physics-based), and AI-driven systems for automated regulatory updates, will be essential.

Therefore, the Advanced Materials Act should address the technological and infrastructural requirements for the development of interoperable holistic Digital Product Passport (DPP)

platforms that can support the collection, storage, access, and analysis of datasets for all types of Advanced Materials – across entire value networks. In parallel, lifecycle traceability of advanced materials should be strengthened through real-world field studies, systematic collection of long-term performance data (including degradation behaviour, in-service conditions, and operational efficiency), and the definition of clear end-of-life recycling strategies.

3. Evidence based recommendation for a coherent EU legislative framework as supported by the Advanced Materials Act

3.1 Increase EU R&I capacities and the uptake of advanced materials

- Develop and implement standardized data formats covering advanced materials composition, properties, manufacturing processes, lifecycle performance, environmental impact, handling, potential toxicity, and end-of-life information.
- Promote the establishment of open-access data repositories to foster transparency and responsible data sharing, as well as seamless connection with Digital Product Passport platforms to enable traceability over the entire value networks and faster compliance with regulations covering the materials operation, safety, recyclability and end-of-life. Incentivize industry to get engaged in targeted collaborative innovation processes together with RTOs. The administrative burden for such collaborations in the current European programmes is simply too high.
- COM/2024/98 relies on the Advanced Materials Academy, which is now in the process of being set up. One concrete aim of this process has been established as training 200 000 learners by 2029 on new developments within advanced materials. It would certainly vitalize European innovation if this aim could be reached.
- The work on the Advanced Materials Academy so far has not taken into account that universities are the main institution for higher and further/continuing education. This is where all the learners that we have promised to train can actually be found. Following COM/2024/98, the universities are to be engaged through a top-down process only. Such processes are often intransparent, distant from practice, and - most problematically - they are slow. This contradicts the simplification objectives of the AMA.
- Instead, there needs to be an active involvement of the universities within the European Economic Area; direct, bottom-up, transparent, and unbureaucratic – i.e., the opposite of what it is now. University faculty should be involved directly through small-scale seed funds for developing further/continuing education specially targeting staff from industry.

3.2 Increase production capacity and availability in the EU

- Mandate standardization/normation processes that enable secure, tamper-proof sharing of advanced materials data, thereby supporting trust, traceability, and the integration of new advanced materials in industrial production and on the market.
- Mandate standardized semantic interoperability frameworks (taxonomies) aligned with technical standards and norms as machine and human readable objects.
- Promote business models, including licensing and service agreements, to facilitate FAIR and equitable access to materials data repositories, to make the Green&Digital Transition process sustainable.
- Incentivize Training on the job, re-skilling and up-skilling of existing workforce to make them fit for the digital age, for example through access to funding for industrial players. Training programs should be also supported by European industrial associations.
- Europe would be well advised to deepen international collaborations including not only in research and development, but also specifically in education and training. European universities must be encouraged to collaborate with world-leading institutions, including an active exchange of personnel or holding of side positions.

3.3 Improve circularity and sustainability

- Connect existing successful initiatives, such as open innovation platforms (OIPs), open innovation test beds (OITBs), and safe-and-sustainable-by-design (SSbD) platforms and tools, with DPP platforms. This approach accelerates the necessary industrial transformation processes towards circularity from innovation to manufacturing.
- Implement a European certificate process for Digital Product Passport platforms based on standards (JTC-24 and others). Establish clear governance mechanisms and viable business models that incentivize participation and long-term sustainability.
- Mandate for a Digital Materials Passport as a complement to the Digital Product Passport. Aligned with the idea that materials are feeding manufacturing of products, the Digital Materials Passport feeds into the Digital Product Passport usually in B2B environments.

3.4 Explore the potential for simplification, burden reduction and the acceleration of procedures

- Implement regulatory sandboxes during collaborative innovation processes taking value networks into account. Regulations which apply to one industrial player in networks only may hamper innovation, regulations should target entire value networks with a focus on products (B2C endpoints).
- Make standards and norms digitally available to RTOs and Higher Education (HE) organizations during collaborative innovation processes with industrial players. It is evident that sector specific norms/regulations are simply too costly for RTOs and HEs that work cross-sectorial thus hampering their consideration already at the onset of innovation processes.

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